

COMPARISON OF DAMAGE CHARACTERIZATION OF COMPOSITE LAMINATES UNDER QUASI-STATIC INDENTATION AND LOW-VELOCITY IMPACT

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SUMMARY

The damage characterizations of laminates are compared between the quasi-static indentation and low-velocity impact under two fiducial parameters, the imposed total energy and the maximum transverse load. The result shows that the two fiducial parameters could be effective at high impact energy level.

Keywords: quasi-static indentation, low-velocity impact, delamination, computer simulation

INTRODUCTION

Composite laminates are susceptible to transverse loads such as low-velocity impact. Under low-velocity impact, the impact-induced damage may be barely visible on the surface of the laminates, but it can considerably reduce their in-plane compressive strength [1].

Several studies show a similarity between quasi-static indentation (QSI) and low-velocity impact testing [2, 3]. It would be very beneficial to simulate an event of low-velocity impact using a quasi-static indentation test, since much more data can be obtained from the test. However, an event of low-velocity impact lasts approximately 6-10 milliseconds, so there is the question as to whether or not a quasi-static indentation could represent a low-velocity impact event. Thus, the focus of this paper is to examine if low-velocity impact and quasi-static indentation give the same damage, and most importantly, amount of delamination damage, for a given fiducial parameter. Aymerich [2] carried out the quasi-static indentation and low-velocity impact tests in order to study the influence of load-rate for a given imposed total energy; Nettles and Douglas [3] compared the size of damage between quasi-static indentation and low-velocity impact tests for a given maximum transverse load. Thus, the focus of the work in this paper is to examine the two fiducial parameters, the imposed total energy and the maximum transverse load, for both low-velocity impact and quasi-static indentation tests.

EXPERIMENT

The intent of this study is to compare quasi-static indentation to low-velocity impact. In order to ensure a comparable analysis of the two events, the tests were conducted based on the same standard test method, ASTM D 7136, with T700/5428 laminates. The sizes

of the specimens are 150 mm × 100 mm and the stacking sequence is [45/90/-45/0]_{4S}. A hemi-spherical impactor or indenter of diameter 16 mm was used. The specimens were supported on four rollers which formed a rectangular window of 100 mm × 75 mm.

Impact tests were carried out on a purpose-built drop weight impact testing machine. The impactor displacement was evaluated by double integration of the contact force. Static tests were carried out utilizing a servo hydraulic testing machine at constant indenter velocity of 0.03 mm/s. The energy in static test was defined as the integration of contact force versus indenter displacement during the loading process.

The extent and distribution of delamination were observed after deply of the damaged specimens. In order to separate individual layers of different orientations, the specimens were heated in an oven.

A summary for experiment is shown in Table 1.

It is observed that there exists a delamination threshold impact energy such as specimen I-75 in Table 1. If the impact energy is below this threshold level the impact does not cause internal delaminations in the laminates. When the impact energy is just above this level, the delaminations take place instantaneously. The delamination threshold specimen in quasi-static indentation test is the S-73 in Table 1.

Table 1 A summary for experiment.

Specimen	Event	Maximum transverse load /KN	The imposed total energy /J
S-71	QSI	9.1	17.8
S-72	QSI	12.6	26.7
S-73	QSI	3.9	3.6
S-74	QSI	7.1	12.5
I-75	Impact	4.0	5.2
I-76	Impact	7.1	17.8
I-77	Impact	9.1	26.7

MODEL DEVELOPMENT

Contact Law

Yang and Sun [4] modified the Hertzian contact law on the basis of results of loading-unloading experiments. This law can be applied to calculate the contact force during both loading and unloading:

Loading:

$$f = k\alpha^{1.5} \quad (1)$$

Where f is the contact force, α is the indentation, and the contact stiffness k is given by

$$k = \frac{4}{3} \sqrt{R_i} \frac{1}{\left[(1 - \nu_i^2) / E_i + 1 / E_t \right]} \quad (2)$$

The respective constants of R_i , ν_i , and E_i are the radius, the Poisson's ratio and Young's modulus of impactor, and E_t is the transverse modulus normal to the fiber-direction of the laminate.

Unloading and reloading:

$$f = f_m \left(\frac{\alpha - \alpha_0}{\alpha_m - \alpha_0} \right)^n \quad (3)$$

Where f_m is the maximum contact force, α_m is the indentation corresponding to f_m , and α_0 is the permanent indentation and can be given by

$$\alpha_0 = \begin{cases} 0 & \alpha_m \leq \alpha_{cr} \\ \alpha_m \left[1 - \left(\frac{\alpha_{cr}}{\alpha_m} \right)^{2/5} \right] & \alpha_m > \alpha_{cr} \end{cases} \quad (4)$$

In the above equation, α_{cr} is the critical indentation and approximately 0.08 mm for Graphite/Epoxy composite materials. The power index n in Equation (3) is 2.5 for unloading and 1.5 for reloading.

Failure Criteria

In the present study, three modes of damage, fiber breakage, matrix cracking, and delamination are considered. The Hashin failure criterion is used for predicting the fiber breakage and matrix cracking. The following criterion [5] is also utilized to predicting the appearance and propagation of delamination of the n th interface:

$$D_1 \left[\left(\frac{\bar{\sigma}_{23}^n}{S} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{\bar{\sigma}_{13}^{n+1}}{S} \right)^2 \right] + D_2 \left(\frac{\bar{\sigma}_{22}^{n+1}}{Y} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{\bar{\sigma}_{33}^{n+1}}{Z} \right)^2 = e_D \geq 1 \quad (5)$$

Where D_1 and D_2 are material constants, $\bar{\sigma}$ represents the average stress in each ply, the subscripts 1,2,3 denote the fiber, in-plane transverse, and out-of-plane directions, respectively, of each ply. The subscripts n and $n+1$ correspond to the upper and lower plies of the n th interface. Z is out-of-plane tensile or compression strength, and S is in-plane shear strength. Y is the transverse tensile or compressive strength. In this study, D_1 is chosen as 6.5 and D_2 is chosen as 1.5 for computer simulation.

Cumulative Damage Model

The bi-phase failure model [6] developed by Pam-Crash is introduced to simulate the cumulative damage. In the bi-phase model, the fracturing damage function $d(\varepsilon)$ is given by

$d(\varepsilon) =$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \frac{\varepsilon - \varepsilon_c}{\varepsilon_1 - \varepsilon_c} d_1 & \varepsilon_c < \varepsilon < \varepsilon_1 \\
 & \frac{\varepsilon - \varepsilon_1}{\varepsilon_2 - \varepsilon_1} (d_2 - d_1) + d_1 & \varepsilon_1 < \varepsilon < \varepsilon_2 \\
 & 1 - (1 - d_2) \frac{\varepsilon_2}{\varepsilon} & \varepsilon_2 < \varepsilon < \infty
 \end{aligned} \tag{6}$$

Where ε_c is the initial threshold strain, and ε_1 , ε_2 are the equivalent strain corresponding to damage coefficient d_1 , d_2 . The damage modulus is given by

$$E(\varepsilon) = (1 - d(\varepsilon))E_0 \tag{7}$$

Where E_0 is the initial elastic modulus.

The bi-phase damage diagram is shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Bi-phase damage diagram

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The test and simulation results are shown in Figures 2-10. All the specimens showed no delamination in the 16th interfaces and this is because they are interfaces between plies of same fiber direction. After lines the two fiducial parameters, imposed total energy and maximum transverse load, will be discussed.

Fiducial Parameter: Imposed Total Energy

In this case, both quasi-static indentation and low-velocity impact tests were carried out based on the two total energies, 17.8 J and 26.7 J. The dynamic response and delamination of laminates are shown in Figures 2-5.

As shown in Figures 2-5, the impact simulation results including the force history and delamination areas correlate well with the experiments. The discrepancy can be also found between the quasi-static indentation test and the corresponding simulation, and this is because the pressure distribution in the contact zone changed significantly.

The total delamination area can be obtained by summing the delamination areas at single interfaces. The respective total delamination areas of S-71, I-76, S-72, and I-77 are 3828 mm^2 , 2842 mm^2 , 4665 mm^2 , and 3929 mm^2 .

Figure 2: Contact force vs. impactor displacement (total energy = 17.8 J)

Figure 3: Delamination Area (total energy = 17.8 J)

Figure 4: Contact force vs. impactor displacement (total energy = 26.7 J)

Figure 5: Delamination Area (total energy = 26.7 J)

In general, at lower impact energy, the impacted laminates showed lower amounts of delamination than the one in the QSI test of the same energy level, but at higher impact energy, the amounts of delamination areas are nearly the same, so the low-velocity impact test can be simulated with a quasi-static indentation test based on this fiducial parameter at the higher impact energy.

Fiducial Parameter: Maximum Transverse load

The two maximum transverse loads, 7.1 KN and 9.1 KN, are chosen as the fiducial parameters. The results are shown in Figures 6-9.

Figure 6: Contact force vs. impactor displacement (maximum load = 7.1 KN)

Figure 7: Delamination Area (maximum load = 7.1 KN)

Figure 8: Contact force vs. impactor displacement (maximum load = 9.1 KN)

Figure 9: Delamination Area (maximum load = 9.1 KN)

The respective total delamination areas of S-74, I-76, S-71, and I-77 are 2420 mm², 2808 mm², 3828 mm², and 3929mm².

It can be seen that static indentation tests can be used to represent low-velocity impact events based on maximum transverse load from Figures 6-9. However, when the impact energy is high enough to make the contact force reach the load capacity of the plate, it is questionable whether or not a quasi-static indentation test can duplicate the damage of the low-velocity impact event for a given maximum transverse load.

Special Case

The delamination threshold tests of QSI and low-velocity impact were carried out. As shown in Figure 10(a), the tests have the same transverse peak load.

In this case, compared with the impacted sample (specimen I-75), the static-loaded one (specimen S-73) showed lower amounts of delaminations. For this reason, nearby the delamination threshold impact energy, simulating a low-velocity impact event with a static test could be hazardous.

Figure 10: The delamination threshold tests of QSI and impact

CONCLUSIONS

1. It is known that there exists a peak load in a quasi-static punch indentation test and this peak load is almost the same as the maximum value that can be achieved in low-velocity impact tests. When the maximum transverse load is lower than the peak load referred above, it could be chosen as the fiducial parameter on the basis of delamination areas for the equivalence of quasi-static indentation and low-velocity impact.
2. At higher energy, the imposed total energy can also be chosen as the fiducial parameter for the equivalence of quasi-static indentation and low-velocity impact, although it has less effective than the maximum transverse load at lower energy.
3. Nearby the delamination threshold impact energy, simulating a low-velocity impact event with a static test could be hazardous since this may lead to underestimation of the delamination areas.

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